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The Challenge of Compensation Management in the Nigeria's Public Service

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Abstract

This work examines compensation management in Nigeria's public service. Compensation is a reward for services rendered by employees in the workplace. It can also be defined as the money and benefits that organizations give to employees in exchange for work done. The paper contends that workers in Nigeria's public service are not adequately compensated, and this gives rise to corruption and other social vices prevalent in the service, such as bribery, inflation of contracts, extortion, nepotism, embezzlement of public funds, misappropriation, over- and under-invoicing, and favoritism, among other degrading practices. It is further argued that compensation packages for Nigeria's public servants are poor compared to those of other African countries. Nigeria's minimum wage of USD 65 is one of the lowest on the continent when compared to countries such as Seychelles, Libya, Morocco, Gabon, and South Africa, which have minimum wages of 432, 322, 281, 256, and 242, respectively. This gloomy scenario exposes Nigeria's civil servants to avoidable temptation in terms of corruption. Poor compensation packages also push Nigeria's civil servants into corrupt practices in order to avoid misery and penury after retirement from service. The paper recommends adequate compensation packages for civil and public servants during and after retirement if corruption in the service is to be curbed. It concludes that the meager compensation packages for Nigeria's public servants are not sufficient to motivate them to give their best to the service. This challenge is compounded by the recent removal of fuel subsidies in the country. The poor compensation packages have placed public servants in a dire financial situation, such that many cannot afford to commute to work daily. This has resulted in the rationing of workdays for public servants, an arrangement that appears to be passively supported by the government.

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Introduction

Individuals do not work in organizations merely for the sake of doing so, but to earn a living. There are few, if any, individuals who may be willing to work for an organization without compensation. Despite altruistic dispositions, individuals are generally unwilling to render services without being rewarded. Otherwise, how would they meet their family and social needs within the larger society?

Findings indicate that even in family-owned enterprises, many individuals may be unwilling to work without compensation for the services they render. Individuals expend their time, energy, and resources (mental, physical, material, and financial) in providing services; therefore, they deserve to be rewarded or compensated for their contributions to the organization. In most cases, workers have also invested time, money, and mental resources in acquiring the skills, knowledge, and ideas they apply in organizational service and thus require appropriate compensation.

Compensation and reward systems are central to human resource management, as individuals are unlikely to offer their services to any organization without the expectation of reward. Once engaged, employees expend their time, effort, energy, and labor in contributing to organizational success. In return, they expect to be adequately rewarded and compensated so that they can meet their personal and social needs.

What is compensation?

Compensation is the reward that individuals receive from organizations in exchange for their labor. In the classical political economy tradition, Karl Marx asserted that the proletariat (workers) have nothing to render to organizations other than their labor, which they expect to be compensated for by the bourgeoisie, that is, the capitalists and the owners of the means of production or those at the controlling heights of the political system.

People who work in an organization are invariably engaged in an exchange relationship (Obi, Onyekwelu, Onwubiko, & Mohammed, 2016). Accordingly, workers exchange their labor for financial rewards. Employers believe that the most

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important obligation they owe their workers is the payment of salaries or wages, as the case may be. Although there are other non-financial rewards, such as recognition, praise, and self-esteem, which workers also consider important, the most valued form of compensation is financial.

According to Norman (2024), compensation refers to the monetary payments (wages, salaries, emoluments, and bonuses, both current and deferred) used to reward employees. Similarly, Riccucci (2017) considers compensation rewards to include direct financial payments as well as indirect payments in the form of fringe benefits. However, these definitions tend to equate compensation primarily with monetary income, whereas compensation extends beyond financial remuneration alone.

Compensation can therefore be understood as encompassing all rewards, such as direct financial payments, indirect payments in the form of benefits, and incentives, received by individuals within an organization, in addition to non-compensatory rewards, including aspects of a positive work environment that enhance employees' self-worth and public esteem (Amujiri, 2021).

For most organizations, compensation in the form of wages, salaries, incentives, and pensions constitutes a significant portion of their annual budgets. Organizations that fail to adequately compensate their workers risk recurrent labor unrest, which is detrimental to organizational success.

According to Obi et al. (2016), there are three basic types of compensation: wages, salaries, and incentives. Wages are payments made on an hourly or weekly basis to workers. Salaries are payments made on an annual rate of pay, usually disbursed monthly, and are generally provided irrespective of the number of hours worked.

Incentives are special compensation packages that are typically performance-based. The *raison d'être* for incentives is to motivate workers to exceed normal performance levels, with the understanding that exceptional performance attracts additional rewards (Mahajan, 2025). Incentives include bonuses, commissions, special allowances, and overtime payments.

It should be noted that no organization can achieve its objectives without the efforts of its workers, and one of the primary means of recognizing this effort is through the provision of reasonable compensation. Conversely, employees may be unable to

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receive financial compensation if the organization for which they work does not generate revenue or achieve its set goals. However, in the civil service, compensation does not depend on profit generation. Salaries in the public service are budgeted for across the financial year, and supplementary budgets are required only when new financial entitlements arise that were not previously provided for.

The civil service renders essential services necessary for the survival of any country. These services are not typically profit-oriented, as the public service is not established to generate profit. To do so would undermine the fundamental role of government in maintaining law and order, providing security, and safeguarding territorial integrity. For instance, institutions such as the prison service, police, armed forces, and local governments are not expected to generate profit before compensating their workers. All government Ministries, Departments, and Agencies (MDAs) draw their salaries from budgetary provisions made by the government for each fiscal year.

Thus, whether or not MDAs generate revenue, their workers' salaries and compensation are guaranteed. This is irrespective of the number of hours worked. The term "*salary*" refers to compensation that is uniform from one pay period to the next and does not depend on hours worked. It is usually fixed and graded according to one's level in the public service hierarchy and is typically received by white-collar workers such as administrators, executives, and professionals.

Compensation through salaries, wages, and incentives constitutes the primary reason individuals offer their services or render their labor to organizations. Few people, if any, are so financially independent that they do not accept monetary remuneration for work performed.

Historical Background of Compensation Management in Nigeria's Public Service

It is generally believed that salaries and wages constitute the most important reason workers render their services to organizations. Thus, efficient compensation management is a prerequisite for achieving organizational goals and objectives, as workers serve as the driving force behind organizational performance.

During the First Republic in Nigeria, the salaries and wages of public officers were determined by the regional governments. According to Njoku (2014), each

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regional government fixed the salaries of its workers based on its ability to pay. As a result, there was no uniformity in salary and wage structures across the country. In addition to differences among regional governments, variations also existed in the salary structures of workers in public corporations, the civil service, the teaching service, and local governments.

The Udoji Civil Service Reform of 1974 introduced a unified structure of grading and pay. It established a seventeen-grade level salary system, with each grade level subdivided into salary steps (Njoku, 2014). This unified salary structure marked the beginning of federal government control over salaries in Nigeria's public service.

During the Second Republic (1979–1983), the National Assembly was empowered to determine the salaries of public officers in the country. The Babangida administration, which assumed office in 1985, implemented far-reaching salary reforms, including the introduction of different salary structures for various professions to reflect diverse job requirements. For example, universities, the judiciary, the police, the armed forces, the prison service, customs, and the immigration service were granted distinct salary structures that were higher than those of the core civil service.

Following the 1988 Dotun Phillips Civil Service Reforms, the Babangida regime appointed the Gray Longe Commission and later the Adamu Fika Panel to review the salary structure in the public service. These bodies introduced significant reforms in compensation management, including substantial salary adjustments and the elongation of the salary structure. This increased the number of steps within each grade level, reduced stagnation, and introduced additional allowances with corresponding financial implications (Ekang, 2016).

The Allison Ayida Panel, appointed by the Sani Abacha regime in 1997, recommended a substantial review of wages and salaries in Nigeria's public service. Following these recommendations, the federal government under General Abdulsalami Abubakar introduced a new pay structure based on a minimum wage of ₦3,000 per month for state and local government workers and ₦3,500 for federal workers, which took effect in September 1998. In 2000, President Olusegun Obasanjo increased the minimum wage to ₦5,500, while in 2011 President Goodluck Jonathan raised it to ₦18,000.

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In April 2019, President Muhammadu Buhari approved an increase in the minimum wage to ₦30,000. This development was initially welcomed by public sector workers. However, on May 14, 2019, the federal government inaugurated the Relativity and Consequential Adjustment Committee, which established a technical sub-committee to develop a template for adjusting public sector salaries. Through the National Salaries, Incomes and Wages Commission, the federal government announced that only public servants earning below ₦30,000 were entitled to the new minimum wage. The Commission's Chairman, Mr. Richard Egbule, stated that the implementation of the new wage would be determined by the Office of the Accountant-General of the Federation and would be backdated to the date the President signed the bill into law.

In July 2024, President Bola Tinubu increased the minimum wage of Nigerian workers to ₦70,000, with consequential adjustments. All 36 states in Nigeria implemented similar measures *mutatis mutandis*.

Major Ways of Determining Wages and Compensation in Nigeria

This section refers to the factors that influence how wages, salaries, and other forms of compensation are administered and managed in Nigeria. Some of these factors are internal and within the control of the organization, while others are external and therefore beyond the organization's control. These factors, in no particular order, include:

i. Government Legislation

This is often referred to as a centralized wage administration system. In this system, the government determines the salaries of its employees. In other words, the salaries of public sector workers are centrally fixed through government laws or legislative instruments. This arrangement largely determines the salaries and compensation of public sector employees in Nigeria. Government intervention in wage issues is intended to forestall possible abuses by some sectors of the economy, protect disadvantaged groups, promote full employment, check inflation, and stimulate demand (Obi et al., 2016).

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Laws establishing a minimum wage make it illegal to pay below or above the stated amount. In Nigeria, salaries, allowances, and other compensation packages are usually determined by the government through appropriate laws and regulations.

ii. The Labor Market

The labor market refers to a setting in which labor and human services are bought and sold. Both the public and private sectors are believed to “purchase” labor from the same labor market. The market operates according to the economic law of demand and supply, which states that when supply exceeds demand, wages tend to fall and compensation becomes relatively low.

During periods of rising unemployment, organizations are in an advantageous position, as they can offer lower wages and still attract qualified manpower. Conversely, during periods of near or full employment, labor can demand higher wages and improved conditions of service. Even in periods of high unemployment, certain specialized skills may continue to attract relatively high wages despite generally unfavorable wage conditions.

iii. Ability to Pay

Organizations differ in their capacity to pay wages because they do not generate the same level of revenue or profit. In the public sector, not all institutions receive the same federal allocations or generate the same internally generated revenue, which results in wage differentials among public sector workers.

For example, staff of local government councils, primary and secondary school boards, and ministries may not receive the same salaries at comparable levels as staff of the Nigerian National Petroleum Corporation (NNPC), the Central Bank, the Federal Inland Revenue Service (FIRS), universities, and research institutes. A similar situation applies in the private sector, where wage differentials are also evident and are largely based on organizational ability to pay. In Nigeria, the telecommunications and oil industries generally offer higher wages than many private educational institutions, reflecting differences in returns on investment and financial capacity.

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iv. Influence of Trade Unions

Trade unions play a central role in advocating for fair wages and benefits for their members. When strong, proactive, and well-coordinated, unions can secure improved wages and conditions of service through collective bargaining. Labor unions often employ strategies such as strikes, threats of strikes, boycotts, and other forms of pressure to obtain concessions from employers. Conversely, weak trade unions may be unable to secure meaningful improvements for their members.

v. Prevailing Wages in the Industry

Most industries operate within established wage structures that are common to their sector. Workers are typically paid within the prevailing wage range of the industry. For example, professors in public universities are generally paid according to a standardized wage structure across federal universities. If the prevailing monthly wage range is between ₦450,000 and ₦550,000, it is unlikely that a professor would accept a salary of ₦200,000 to ₦300,000.

Although some state or private universities may offer higher wages to attract and retain highly qualified personnel, most institutions and organizations tend to pay close to the sectoral average. Geographical location also plays a significant role in wage determination. Certain locations attract higher wages across sectors, particularly in the case of multinational companies that maintain different wage structures for different operational locations. As a result, individuals holding the same position and performing similar duties within the same organization may receive different wages depending on their location.

vi. Productivity

According to Obi et al. (2016), individuals are employed and compensated because they are expected to be productive and to contribute to the achievement of organizational goals and objectives. Employers generally seek a workforce that enhances organizational performance and profitability. In political economy terms, workers are expected to create surplus value that supports the payment of wages.

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Surplus value is commonly defined as the difference between the wages paid to a worker and the value of what the worker produces. This implies that the worker's compensation is less than the total value of the product of their labor (Obo, 2017). Workers are therefore expected to generate surplus value that facilitates the payment of their wages, all things being equal.

However, this dynamic is often considered less applicable in the public service, where workers typically do not have clearly defined productivity targets. In the public sector, wage structures are primarily determined by government laws and regulations, as well as the effectiveness of labor unions in negotiating wages and compensation, among other factors. This is also influenced by the ability to pay, as there is little justification for establishing a salary structure that cannot be financially sustained (Oluwayemisi, 2025).

Benefits of Good Compensation Administration

Ezeali and Esiagu (2009) in Ekang (2020) have listed the following as benefits of compensation management to organizations:

- i. It encourages complete trust on both the employer and employee if the degree of performance is fair, reasonable, and just on both sides.
- ii. Good compensation management encourages accurate measurement of the work content.
- iii. It helps to achieve rational wage structure and administration.
- iv. It helps to discourage wage inequalities.
- v. It promotes industrial harmony.
- vi. It encourages an increase in productivity and profitability of the organization.
- vii. It leads to development and rapid increase in the national economy.
- viii. It helps to discourage favoritism, nepotism, traditional attitudes, and exploitative decisions.
- ix. It enhances the practice of collective bargaining by the organization.

The exchange process between the employee and the organization

Organizations are social entities that help man to achieve purpose in life. Man cannot really live life outside organizations. At one stage or another, man finds himself in organizations, either working to earn a living or fulfilling some other purpose. At times he may find himself managing such an organization (Ekang, 2020).

Man depends so much on organizations for his survival. Outside organizations, man may not be able to make any meaning in life. It therefore becomes important to look at the exchange process between employee and organization. This will be diagrammatically presented thus:

Figure 1: The relationship between man and organization

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Organizations typically employ individuals based on the knowledge, ideas, and skills they possess. Employees often invest time, money, and other resources in acquiring the skills, knowledge, creativity, and competencies they bring to the workplace. They are expected to deploy these attributes in the service of the organization and to devote their time and effort to ensuring that the organization benefits from their expertise. In this way, workers contribute to the fulfillment of organizational goals and objectives.

It is generally acknowledged that organizations seek to attract and retain a productive workforce that can facilitate the achievement of their goals and, in some cases, enhance profitability. However, an organization's ability to attract a highly productive workforce largely depends on its capacity to offer competitive wages and favorable working conditions, particularly in situations where the supply of labor exceeds demand in the labor market (Ekang, 2020).

From the employee's perspective, there is a desire for an engaging work environment and fair compensation for services rendered. Employees tend to resist unfair treatment, as such conditions may result in industrial conflict. Organizations therefore assume responsibilities such as the timely payment of salaries, the provision of fringe benefits, the creation of status and recognition for employees, the generation of employment opportunities for the public, and the enhancement of workers' social opportunities both within and outside the organization.

Government workers, in particular, often receive social recognition because they exercise discretionary authority that can influence people's lives during the implementation of public policies. The social and occupational opportunities available to public servants are often not accessible to most members of the general public.

This circumstance places public servants in a distinct category. For example, the authority exercised by magistrates, judges, and justices in delivering judgments is derived from their role as agents of the state and would not exist on an individual basis outside government employment. Similar forms of authority are exercised by the police, armed forces, prison officials, customs officers, immigration officers, and road safety officers. Without their status as public servants, such individuals would not possess the institutional power to exercise authority over others in their individual capacities.

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Compensation Management in Nigeria's Public Service

The expectation of receiving salaries, wages, and other compensatory packages is a primary reason workers render their services to organizations. It has been asserted, and is maintained here, that few individuals are sufficiently wealthy or patriotic to work for government without salaries or other forms of compensation. Workers provide services to organizations in exchange for income, which they use to meet their individual and social needs.

Compensation management in Nigeria's public service is largely determined through legislation and laws that are binding on all sectors of the federal public service. State governments are generally permitted to negotiate with their workers on the level of compensation they are able to pay, contingent upon their financial capacity. This often results in salary differentials between federal and state government workers within Nigeria's public service. For example, in some cases, state universities pay their staff more than federal universities, and similar variations occur in other sectors.

Past minimum wage increases in Nigeria include ₦125 (1981) under President Shehu Shagari; ₦250 (1989/1990) under President Ibrahim Babangida; ₦3,000 (1998) under General Abdulsalami Abubakar; ₦5,500 (2000) under President Olusegun Obasanjo; ₦18,000 (2011) under President Goodluck Jonathan; and ₦70,000 (2024) under President Bola Tinubu.

In April 2019, President Muhammadu Buhari approved a minimum wage of ₦30,000. On May 18, 2024, President Tinubu approved a ₦70,000 minimum wage for Nigerian workers. However, some state governments negotiated higher figures, such as ₦85,000 in Rivers State and ₦80,000 in Akwa Ibom State, among others.

Compared to many other countries, Nigeria pays one of the lowest minimum wages in Africa. The minimum wage refers to the lowest statutorily required wage that workers can earn; it is illegal for employers to pay employees below this amount as stipulated by federal law. Several African countries maintain higher minimum wages than Nigeria. For instance, Seychelles reportedly has a minimum wage of USD 432 per month, Libya USD 322, Morocco USD 281, Gabon USD 256, South Africa USD 242, Mauritius USD 240, Equatorial Guinea USD 200, the Republic of Congo USD 154, Algeria USD 151, Kenya USD 140, Cape Verde USD 132, Comoros Islands USD 125,

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Lesotho USD 112, the Democratic Republic of Congo USD 125, Tunisia USD 110, Chad USD 102, Côte d'Ivoire USD 102, Senegal USD 94, and Liberia USD 91, while Nigeria's minimum wage in 2022 was approximately USD 65 per month.

Low minimum wages have been associated with the attractiveness of corrupt practices within Nigeria's public service. According to Ekang (2016), since Nigeria attained independence on October 1, 1960, corruption has remained a persistent challenge in the country's social and political life. Successive governments since 1966 have attempted, albeit unsuccessfully, to eliminate it from public life. Efforts to combat corruption in the public sector have yielded limited success.

Because salaries paid to many civil servants are relatively low and insufficient to guarantee a comfortable standard of living, some resort to corrupt practices as a means of alleviating poverty. It is often observed that public servants who live above the poverty line, particularly at the lower levels of the civil service, may rely on such practices to supplement their income.

According to Daniel (2019), "corruption is one of the greatest problems of the Nigerian public service." Corruption manifests in various forms, including bribery, contract inflation, extortion, nepotism, embezzlement of public funds, misappropriation, over- or under-invoicing, and favoritism, among other practices. On this basis, some scholars, such as Ikejiani-Clarke (2001), cited in Obi et al. (2016), have attempted to justify the persistence of corruption in the public service. According to this view, corruption provides resources that enable public servants to support themselves, educate their children, and prepare for life after retirement.

Many scholars agree that concerns about post-retirement life motivate some civil and public servants to engage in corrupt practices in order to prepare financially for retirement. This is attributed to the perception that salaries and compensation packages are insufficient to ensure a secure post-retirement life. Where a retiring civil servant does not own a home, lacks a means of transportation, has children still in school, and is unable to meet medical or basic living expenses, anxiety about retirement becomes pronounced. Consequently, the fear of retirement becomes a significant influence on the behavior of serving civil servants.

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This situation suggests that compensation packages in Nigeria's civil service are widely perceived as inadequate and insufficient to protect retirees from poverty. This is particularly evident after retirement, when many former civil servants face financial hardship, including the lack of personal housing, limited mobility, difficulty supporting their children's education, and challenges in meeting basic living and medical expenses.

Writing specifically about retiring teachers in Nigeria's public service, Etuk (2000) found that teachers prioritize current financial rewards, pensions, and medical care, in that order. In effect, retirement benefits rank immediately after present income in their considerations. Given the importance of pensions, Etuk (2000) argued that employers should give greater attention to retirement welfare. Retired teachers, in particular, should be adequately supported by their former employers. Some improvements have been noted, such as the introduction of retirement seminars six months before teachers retire. However, further measures, including continued medical care after retirement and the inclusion of retired staff in organizational health insurance schemes, were recommended. These observations may also be applicable to other categories of civil and public servants in Nigeria's public service.

Summary and Conclusion

This paper examined compensation management in Nigeria's public service. Compensation was defined as the reward individuals receive from organizations in exchange for their labor and contributions to organizational growth and success. Two main types of compensation were identified: direct and indirect compensation.

Direct compensation consists of wages, salaries, bonuses, and commissions. Indirect compensation includes benefits provided by the employer that are not part of direct financial payments, such as insurance and vacation entitlements. The paper argued that compensation packages in Nigeria's public service are inadequate and insufficient to support a meaningful standard of living for public servants.

This situation has prompted many public servants to engage in corrupt practices in order to supplement their income and live above the poverty line. As a result, corruption is perceived as a means of survival and advancement within the public service.

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The paper recommended that civil and public servants be adequately compensated both during active service and after retirement. It maintained that the fear of retiring into financial hardship and insecurity often motivates some civil servants to engage in corrupt practices. Furthermore, inadequate compensation packages were found to be insufficient to motivate public sector workers to perform optimally in the service of the nation.

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